

5-Substituted-1,3,4-Oxadiazoles and Related Compounds as Possible Fungicides

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Seven 5-aryl/aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones, three 3-hydroxymethyl-5-aryl/aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones, forty 3-arylaminomethyl/ethylideno/benzylideno-aryl/aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones and thirty N,N'-bis-(3-methylene/ethylideno/benzylideno-5-aryl/aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione)-benzidines/*p*-phenylene diamines have been synthesised with a view to study their antifungal activity. Most of these compounds have been screened for their antifungal activity against *A. niger* and *A. flavus* and found to be antifungal.

THE oxadiazole ring is associated with antifungal¹, hypoglycemic², analgesic³, herbicidal⁴ and antimycobacterial⁵ properties. The -SH group attached to a heterocyclic nucleus may induce fungicidal activity⁶. Compounds containing N-C-S linkage are reported as antiirradiation agents⁷, anthelmintics⁸, fungicides⁹, insecticides¹⁰, nematocides¹¹, antitubercular¹² and pesticides¹³. The oxoanalogs of 5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles are reported to exert adverse effect against several pathogenic fungi¹⁴. Kubo et al¹⁵ investigated the herbicidal activity of a large number of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles and concluded that presence of a halophenoxymethyl group at 5-position enhances the activity of the compound and oxadiazole ring has no special effect. Caldwell¹⁶ have reported that 3-substituted aminomethyl-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones are tuberculostatic and fungicidal. Similarly, 3,5-disubstituted 1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones have strong pesticidal¹⁵ and hypoglycemic² activity. Several piperazine derivatives have been used as pesticides and possess antileukemic, antihypertensive, neuroleptic, adrenolytic and antifungal properties¹⁷. Some benzidine derivatives were found to have antimicrobial activity and presence of a heterocyclic moiety increased their activity¹⁸. Keeping this in view the title compounds have been prepared.

5-Aryl/aryloxymethyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazole-2-thiones (I), required in this work, have been obtained by the reaction of aroyl and aryloxyacetyl hydrazines¹⁹ with carbon disulphide in the presence of alkali²⁰. Reaction of (I) with formaldehyde gave their 3-hydroxymethyl derivatives (II), whereas condensation with aldehydes in the presence of amines²¹ resulted in the formation of 3-amino methyl derivatives(III). However, use of *p*-phenylenediamine and benzidine in place of amines, in the latter reaction, led to the formation of corresponding N-N'-bis(3,5-disubstituted 1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione) *p*-phenylenediamines and benzidines(IV) respectively :

The analytical data of the compounds, thus obtained, are summarised in Tables 1-4.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected.

Aroyl/aryloxyacetyl hydrazines :

These were prepared by the method of L. Conti¹⁹.

5-Aryl/aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones(I)²⁰

An aroyl/aryloxyacetyl hydrazine (0.05M) was added to a 10 ml aqueous solution of KOH (0.05M). To this 200 ml of ethanol (95%) was added. A clear solution was thus obtained. To this carbon disulphide (1.0M) was added and the resulting

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mixture refluxed for six hours. It was concentrated to a small volume and then poured into ice water. The resulting mixture was filtered. The filtrate on acidification with cold 4*N*.HCl gave a precipitate which was filtered, washed and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol.

3-Hydroxymethyl-5-aryl/aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones(II) :

To an ethanolic solution (50 ml) of 5-aryl/aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones (0.02*M*), formaldehyde (0.02*M*) was added and the resulting solution refluxed for thirty minutes. Ethanol was distilled off and the remaining product poured into water. The solid separating out was filtered, washed and recrystallised.

3-Arylamino-methyl / ethylideno / benzylideno-5-aryl/aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones(III)²¹ :

5-Aryl/aryloxymethyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione (0.01*M*) was dissolved in a minimum quantity of ethanol and kept in an ice bath. To this 0.01*M* of formaldehyde/acetaldehyde/benzaldehyde was added. An arylamine (0.01*M*) dissolved in a minimum quantity of ethanol was then added slowly to this ice cold mixture. The resulting mixture was swirled gently and then left in the ice-bath for three hours. The precipitated solid was filtered off and recrystallised.

N, N'-bis-(3-methylene/ethylideno/benzylideno-5-aryl/aryloxymethyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione)-benzidines/p-phenylenediamines(IV) :

5-Aryl/aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione

(0.01*M*) was dissolved in ethanol and cooled in an ice-bath. To this formaldehyde/acetaldehyde/benzaldehyde (0.01*M*) was added. An ethanolic solution of benzidine/*p*-phenylene diamine (0.005*M*) was now added to it dropwise with swirling. The mixture was kept in an ice-bath for three hours. The solid separating out was filtered, washed with cold ethanol, dried and recrystallised.

Fungicidal activity :

All the compounds of Tables 1,2,4 and thirty five compounds of Table 3 were screened for their antifungal activity against *A. niger* and *A. flavus* by agar plate technique^{22,23} at three different concentrations namely 1 : 1,000, 1 : 10,000 and 1 : 100,000. All the compounds display nearly same level of fungicidal activity against both the fungi and possess moderate fungicidal activity. In general fungicidal activity for different groups at position five decreases as 4-F-C₆H₄-, 2-NO₂-C₆H₄-OCH₃-, 4-NO₂-C₆H₄-, 3-NO₂-C₆H₄-, 4-Cl-3-Me-C₆H₃-OCH₃-, 2,4-Me₂-C₆H₃-OCH₃-, 4-Me-C₆H₄-, 2-Me-C₆H₄-, 3-Me-C₆H₄-. All the compounds derived from oxadiazoles show higher fungicidal activity than the parent compounds. Introduction of benzylideno and ethyleno groups has been found to decrease the fungicidal activity as compared to methyl group and introduction of *p*-phenylene diamine moiety in place of benzidine does not have any significant effect towards the fungicidal activity of the compounds.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF (I)

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield (%)	Molecular formula	N %	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	2-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	145	90	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	14.43	14.58
2.	3-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	167	86	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ OS	—	14.58
3.	4-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	196	92	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ OS	—	14.58
4.	4-F-C ₆ H ₄ -	188-4	80	C ₉ H ₈ FN ₃ OS	14.30	14.36
5.	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ -	174-5	60	C ₉ H ₇ N ₃ O ₄ S	16.48	16.60
6.	4-Cl-3-Me-C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	125-3	85	C ₁₀ H ₉ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	10.78	10.91
7.	2,4-Me ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	170	84	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	11.70	11.86

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA OF (II)

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield (%)	Molecular formula	N %	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	2-Me-C ₆ H ₄	113	95	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₂ S	12.50	12.61
2.	4-Cl-3-Me-C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	183	90	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	9.71	9.77
3.	2,4-Me ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	190	90	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ S	10.47	10.52

TABLE 3—ANALYTICAL DATA OF (III)

Sl. No.	R	R'	X	M.P. °C	Yield (%)	Molecular formula	N%	
							Found	Calcd.
1.	2-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	124	90	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	12.54	12.67
2.	3-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	162	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	12.53	12.67
3.	4-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	167	94	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	12.50	12.67
4.	4-F-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	126	85	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClFN ₂ O ₂ S	12.44	12.55
5.	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ -	H	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	164	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₃ O ₄ S	14.12	14.26
6.	4-Cl-3-Me-C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	H	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	156	80	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	10.48	10.60
7.	2,4-Me ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	H	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	186	85	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	11.12	11.18
8.	2-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	Ph-NO ₂ H ₂ -	99	87	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.80	12.92
9.	3-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	Ph-NC ₂ H ₅ -	101	85	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.70	12.92
10.	4-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	Ph-NC ₂ H ₅ -	105	90	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.82	12.92
11.	4-Cl-3-Me-C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	H	Ph-NC ₂ H ₅ -	130	80	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	10.68	10.78
12.	2,4-Me ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	H	Ph-NC ₂ H ₅ -	89	81	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	11.27	11.38
13.	2-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	Ph ₂ N-	102	86	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	11.16	11.26
14.	3-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	Ph ₂ N-	130	82	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	11.17	11.26
15.	4-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	Ph ₂ N-	134	90	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	11.12	11.26
16.	4-F-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	Ph ₂ N-	83	75	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ FN ₂ O ₂ S	—	11.17
17.	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ -	H	Ph ₂ N-	85	70	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄ S	12.77	12.90
18.	4-Cl-3-Me-C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	H	Ph ₂ N-	163	80	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	9.84	9.60
19.	2,4-Me ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	H	Ph ₂ N-	183	82	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	10.00	10.07
20.	3-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	114	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	12.03	12.05
21.	4-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	105	82	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	12.05	12.15
22.	4-F-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	S*	76	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClFN ₂ O ₂ S	—	12.05
23.	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ -	CH ₃	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	181	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClN ₃ O ₄ S	13.63	13.77
24.	4-Cl-3-Me-C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	CH ₃	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	146	80	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	10.15	10.24
25.	2,4-Me ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	CH ₃	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	173	78	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	10.78	10.80
26.	2-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	S*	80	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	—	12.15
27.	3-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	S*	76	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	—	12.15
28.	3-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	S*	84	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	—	12.15
29.	2-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	2-C ₆ H ₄ O-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	S*	81	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	—	11.83
30.	3-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	2-C ₆ H ₄ O-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	109	74	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	11.72	11.83
31.	4-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	2-C ₆ H ₄ O-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	81	85	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	11.71	11.83
32.	4-F-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	2-C ₆ H ₄ O-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	S*	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ FN ₂ O ₂ S	—	11.73
33.	4-Cl-3-Me-C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	CH ₃	2-C ₆ H ₄ O-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	175	82	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	10.00	10.01
34.	2,4-Me ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	CH ₃	2-C ₆ H ₄ O-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	174	80	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	10.38	10.52
35.	4-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	Ph-NC ₂ H ₅ -	120	90	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.25	12.39
36.	2-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	Ph-	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	110	81	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	10.18	10.30
37.	3-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	Ph-	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	57	80	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	10.12	10.30
38.	4-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	Ph-	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	95	85	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	10.12	10.30
39.	4-Cl-3-Me-C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	Ph-	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	49	75	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.75	8.89
40.	2,4-Me ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	Ph-	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	177	78	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.17	9.30

* Semi solid.

TABLE 4—ANALYTICAL DATA OF (IV)

Sl. No.	R	R'	n	M.P. °C	Yield (%)	Molecular formula	N%	
							Found	Calcd.
1.	2-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	2	179	84	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	14.06	14.19
2.	3-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	2	176	80	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	14.10	14.19
3.	4-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	2	134	90	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	14.08	14.19
4.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	2	180	75	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	17.04	17.12
5.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	2	189	90	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	17.04	17.12
6.	4-Cl-3-Me-C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	H	2	128	82	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	11.50	11.64
7.	2,4-Me ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	H	2	150	85	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	12.22	12.35
8.	2-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	2	110	82	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	13.49	13.35
9.	3-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	2	122	75	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	13.45	13.35
10.	4-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	2	125	86	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	13.47	13.35
11.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	2	134	72	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	16.29	16.42
12.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	2	137	78	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	16.35	16.42
13.	4-Cl-3-Me-C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	CH ₃	2	113	80	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	11.22	11.21
14.	2,4-Me ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	CH ₃	2	131	81	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	11.80	11.86
15.	4-Cl-3-Me-C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	Ph-	2	136	78	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	9.51	9.62
16.	2-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	1	174	87	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	16.19	16.28
17.	3-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	1	177	84	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	16.16	16.28
18.	4-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	1	155	92	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	16.19	16.28
19.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	1	159	79	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	19.30	19.39
20.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	1	166	88	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	19.29	19.38
21.	4-Cl-3-Me-C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	H	1	142	86	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	15.37	15.44

(Table 4 Contd.)

Sl. No.	R	R	n	M.P. °C	Yield (%)	Molecular formula	N%	
							Found	Calcd.
22.	2,4-Me ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	H	1	125	86	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	13.82	13.91
23.	2-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	1	114	85	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	15.35	15.44
24.	3-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	1	116	82	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	15.34	15.44
25.	4-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	1	114	90	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	15.37	15.44
26.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	1	132	74	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	18.40	18.48
27.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	1	146	81	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	18.37	18.48
28.	4-Cl-3-Me-C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	CH ₃	1	120	83	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ ClN ₂ O ₄ S ₂	12.40	12.47
29.	2,4-Me ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃ -	CH ₃	1	152	81	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	13.20	13.29
30.	4-Me-C ₆ H ₄ -	Ph-	1	130	80	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	12.42	12.57

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